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THE USE OF SUPERSTITIONS IN THE LIFE OF ENGLISH SPEAKING COUNTRIES AND THEIR TYPES ACCORDING TO SITUATIONS

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ANNOTATION

Learning a language is not only about linguistic factors of a language, it is but also about learning about cultural background, expressions and beliefs. This article focuses on superstitious beliefs and analysis of them according to their types. Collecting superstitions of English speaking countries and grouping them according to their use are defined as the main purpose of the article. Studying this topic field has caught our attention due to its interesting background with various samples and examples.

Key words: superstition, types of superstition, wedding superstitions, animal superstitions, linguaculturology, cognitive perspective, superstitious people

АННОТАЦИЯ

Изучение языка связано не только с лингвистическими факторами языка, но и с изучением культурного происхождения, выражений и убеждений. В данной статье основное внимание уделяется суеверным верованиям и их анализу по типам. Основная цель исследования — собрать суеверия в англоязычных странах и сгруппировать их по употреблению. Изучение этой тематической области привлекло наше внимание из-за ее интересной предыстории с различными образцами и примерами.

Ключевые слова: суеверие, виды суеверий, свадебные суеверия, суеверия о животных, лингвокультурология, Когнитивная перспектива, суеверные люди.

ANNOTATSIYA

Til o'rganish nafaqat tilning lingvistik omillarini, balki madaniy jihatdan kelib chiqishini, tili o'rganilayotgan xalqning madaniy ifodalari va e'tiqodlarini ham o'rganishdir. Ushbu maqolada irimga bo'lgan e'tiqodlarga va ularning turlariga ko'ra tahliliga e'tibor qaratilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi ingliz tilida so'zlashadigan mamlakatlardagi irimlarni to'plash va ularni qo'llanilishiga qarab guruhlashdir. Ushbu mavzuni o'rganish turli xil namunalar va misollar bilan qiziqarli ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lganligi sababli bizning e'tiborimizni tortdi.

Kalit so'zlar: xurofot, xurofot turlari, to'y xurofotlari, hayvonlar xurofotlari, lingvakulturologiya, kognitiv nuqtai nazar, xurofotli odamlar

Introduction

The lives of people are full of unwritten rules, sometimes their beliefs in supernatural forces control them and they mostly follow them unconsciously. One of the widest notions among them is superstition that has no single definition; these beliefs vary so extensively that mostly people are grouped into cultures according to their diversity. In English speaking countries people live with these individual beliefs and these superstitions have become part and parcel of their life. Superstition has no single definition and it has rarely been proved to be true or practically, it may seem to be real and coincide with some situations; these situations make people believe in superstitions. English people use various types of superstitions in their lives, the superstitions have been mostly inherited from their ancestors. Historically, the will to comprehend, to control and to sense was the main objective end of the primitives [1, p. 35]. Therefore, diverse intentions took a start of appearing in order to better understand the mysterious seemed world. According to life examples and some research results, superstitions are often used in outskirts of English cities where still ancient traditions are alive. Psychologists who have investigated the relationship of superstition with the personality and morality of individuals explain that those trusting people in superstitions do this because they try to reduce anxiety and take the control of bad luck in their life. Consequently, they feel more confident, have peace in their heart and soul. Furthermore, engaging with superstitions gives people positive attitude and they think they are fearless [11, p. 21]. Admittedly, it should be mentioned that even if some people deny believing in some beliefs and rituals (as considered plausible by most) they still use them in their life situations, particularly in challenging ones. Studying the notion of superstitions and their use in various cultures are still disputable issue. Specifically, the relationship between religion and superstitions has constantly appeared in the centre of scientific discussions. While studying this topic we tried to look at it from linguaculturological point of view and some authentic and interesting examples have been found. Analyzing them we have learned that there exist huge contrast and little similarities among superstitions and their use among nations. With thorough cognitive notion, their use variety and deep-rooted background – superstitions entitle in-depth research and investigation; obviously, we have been trying to investigate profoundly about previous studies, scientists' research, conceptualizations and findings to acquire enough amount of data on the topic.

Background of the study

However, in 18th-19th –centuries people commenced to understand that not everything tightly depended on that unproven beliefs; and in that period, particularly, the relationship between religion and superstitions was hotly debated. McCartney studies the fear of people towards events and objects, he pays his thorough attention on the root of some superstitions that humans experience collaboratively or individually [17, p.425]. As he and other superstition-interested scientists state that people had to believe in superstitions when they lost their control over events and outcomes or even they got soothing believing in the situations that were growing dubious. Mostly, people with scientific knowledge or without consider the notion of `magic` and `superstition` the same thing.

Well-known psychologist Gustav Jahoda, who studied psychological sides of superstitions, varies them between “casual superstitions” and “coincidental superstitions” [21, p.38]. The former one, as explained refers to a conscious belief between two events (finding a horseshoe is believed to bring good luck and prosperity), while coincidental superstitions shows correlation of behavior and outcome (Romans believed in the strong correlation between Gods and natural phenomena).

According to the analysis of some superstitions, annual great financial loss may happen because of strong belief of people in superstitions. Real examples of those are related to the day of the week `Friday` when it coincides 13th date of the month. `Friday 13th` caused money-related catastrophes, namely even between \$800 million and \$900 million loss for the USA business world. It is possibly because most people become reluctant to travel or they are afraid of making major purchases, or they feel fear of conducting business due to that unlucky and scary superstition.

McCartney studies the fear of people towards events and objects, he pays his thorough attention on the root of some superstitions that humans experience collaboratively or individually. As he and other superstition-interested scientists state that people had to believe in superstitions when they lost

their control over events and outcomes or even they got soothing believing in the situations that were growing dubious. Mostly, people with scientific knowledge or without consider the notion of `magic` and `superstition` the same thing. Magic is uncertain, instable and it is carried out by special individuals, who are called magicians among nations, while superstitions are the result of humans` actions. They are not fully aware of the result of their beliefs, yet follow them in order feel secure to some little extent. The findings of some scientists defined some essentials results, such as the analysis of Buhrman and Zaugg. In their study they have found a direct relationship between level of religiosity and believing in superstition. As Bleak and Fredrick inferred that there is no relationship between them. According to another study, that religious and non-religious people`s beliefs nearly appeared to be in equal level, however people who religiously brought up have more tendencies toward the superstitious or metaphysical beliefs [18, p. 55].

Research methods: Collection of superstitions related to **English** speaking countries and grouping them is a process where each feature of them is taken into consideration. Studying this topic field has caught our attention due to its interesting background with various samples and examples. While researching we mainly used empirical method, concepts underpinning different superstitions through the lens of cognitive, linguacultural perspectives. Using articles, paperwork and some internet sites, we have found 7 types of superstitions.

Types of superstitions according to their usage. Superstitions can be divided into several types depending on their use, after having researched we have found following types of them:

Food superstitions: apple peels can predict true love – this superstition may appear among superstitious young people, as they believe if they can peel an apple unstoppably as long as it breaks and look at to find any letter that appeared letter will be the first letter of their true love. Next superstition is about banana, fishermen everytime try to refuse to take bananas on a fishing board. It has several related historical events, once a fisherman took a bunch of bananas with him onto the board and felt ill badly or another story explains fisherman`s poor catch that day. So, supposing you do go fishing with a superstitious angler and must bring a banana—hide it somewhere before it ruins your day. One more very interesting superstition from the life of the English is throwing rice at the weddings. This superstition means a celebration of bride and groom`s life-long vows, hoping for long, happy and prosperous life newlywed couples hand out tiny bundles of uncooked rice for well-wishers to toss in their direction as they leave. According to this old superstition, gifting a knife to each other friends run the risk of "cutting" their friendship. In English speaking countries, Christmas is one of the most important period of the year, interesting and live side of this holiday is that Christmas is fraught with `colourful` and `endless` superstitions. To take one example from them, English people believe cutting a cake before Christmas Eve and not leaving a piece of it till Christmas Day is the meaning of bad luck [26, p. 182-207]

Sport superstitions: superstitions in the world of sport are quite unusual than others, sportsmen always stick to them since they believe that following superstitions will certainly bring them success and best scores. Some of them even never throw away old part of their clothes. For instance, Michael Jordan, famous basketball player, never forgets to wear his blue shorts under his uniform as he believes that this brings him good fortune and luck. While researching we have found that among sports people baseball players are considered to be the most superstitious ones. In that sport spitting into hand before picking up the bat is believed to bring good luck [6, p.12]. This superstition is rooted in some events that might have probably proved that if they keep to this superstition, they will mostly win. Sticking a wad of gum on a player's hat is also believed to bring good luck, whereas if we look at it from the side of medicine or aesthetics it is not that right and accurate. Not washing any of your gear or apparel (even your underwear) will keep a winning streak going. Another superstition relevant to baseball players` life in sports is that some basketballers sleep with their bat to avoid bad luck in the upcoming play. However, we should remark that majority of superstitions serve for goodness, one of them is maybe created for following accuracy rules when they wipe the soles of their sneakers for good luck only for the favor of being clean. As a result, this habit only serves for healthy lifestyle and for peace in the soul [3, p. 148]. Not always every superstition in sport life can be for goodness,

for example, continuing a winning streak, wear the same clothes without cleaning in bowling. How is it possible not to wash and clean after sweaty play and continue in this spirit?

Wedding superstitions: wedding day is the day when you never want to meet with unfortunate things, perhaps this intention often makes people believe in wedding superstitions from the first steps of bride and groom. Even those superstitions have already become wedding traditions in the UK. As wedding days are always complicated with everything related to wedding preparations, before – wedding emotions, clothes, food choice, words and the rings, all of these may cause exhaustion and confusion. As a result, to deal with all couples or their close ones begin to believe in something unproven, and here several wedding superstitions are born. According to one popular superstition, if brides want to have everything as bright as they desire, they believe that they should combine their wedding appearance with ‘something old, something new, something borrowed and something blue’ as part of their wedding garment. This rhythmic content of that superstition proves that the English people frequently address to this belief. Old thing can be bride’s mother’s jewelers or wedding dress or anything borrowed may be a purse taken from a friend. [25, p. 65]. Therefore, it is not a tradition to wear everything new in English speaking countries as most Asian brides do. Regarding to dresses of brides there is another rhythmic superstition – “Married in white, you have chosen right; married in black, you’ll wish yourself back”. As we see, white color is considered to be one of the good evil causal. This superstition is taken as national tradition from a lot of countries all over the world. Even the day of the week is so important that couples pay great attention and choose it carefully. There is an interesting little poem about this superstition:

‘Monday for health,
Tuesday for wealth,
Wednesday best of all,
Thursday for losses,
Friday for crosses,
Saturday for no luck at all’

It has been mentioned before that future bride and grooms may try to be attentive for their every step if they are truly superstitious, taking example of the things that they meet on their way – if bride meet lambs or if groom meets policemen and clergymen, they believe that it is luck, if they meet pigs or something unpleasant that is believed to be misfortune. Another superstition that dominated many brides’ preparations is also one of the oldest. According to this superstition, a bride should never try on all her wedding outfit in one go before the big day. Instead, she should leave at least one item of clothing or an accessory to one side or risk lots of bad luck. During try-ons, brides were also warned not to look at themselves in full-length mirrors.

Animal superstitions: in terms of animal superstitions cats-related superstition is the most famous one, apparently most people either they are superstitious or not believe in it. Both intriguingly and astonishingly, cats of black color have always become the main trend among the superstitious. In some situations people claim black cat as a cause leading to failure or misfortune, in the meantime other people state that their cross your can be the sign of something positive. In terms of some jobs the condition becomes much clear, such as miners and sailors, in most part of UK, try to keep away from having that animal in that color in their working place and they view them as hazard. While in one unity of England called Cornwall black cat visit into mine cause anger and resentment of mine workers, even work is mostly stopped straight away and the most astonishing point of the situation is that cat has to be killed before starting the work again. Believing a black cat as a bad luck began in ancient Germany, in 13th century; in religious books there was a note “In it, black cats were declared an incarnation of Satan,” originally beginning to suppress newly upcoming creed in Germany, called Luciferians, but quickly spread across Europe.” However, if a cat crosses path, Chinese people do not feel surprise and be grateful as they are considered a blessing[14, p. 45]; Although the origin of the belief of seeing black cats as a symbol of wealth associates with Japan, later Chinese adopted it. Basing on an internet material, we have learnt that Egyptians treasure cats as a divine symbol. Addressing to mythology of Greeks, we may see that cats played a crucial role in those myths, particularly they related to the goddess of death, magic and witchcraft-Hecate who keeps

cat as a pet and familiar. Evidences and examples are abundant, they seem to be waiting to be studied.

Rabbits are symbol of luck and good fortune. If English people used to keep rabbits at their home in the past, later they began to keep the feet of rabbits in their pocket or in their bag, nowadays they attach an artificial rabbit foot into their key ring. It is really strange how did they keep a foot of dead rabbit in their pocket?! There is an interesting story about owls, if people see an owl in daytime, firstly it means bad luck, secondly New Zealanders regard owls like harbingers of accident and death. Another interesting belief appears in the life of Welsh villagers, if they ever hear the hoot of an owl, they believe that any of the local girls is going to lose her virginity.

Robins are regarded as a symbol of bravery, this sense stems from a historical event related a tradition. The tradition is about the little history of red breast of robin. According to Christian folklore, once robin (personification from folklore) defeated the Crown of Thorns and took the throne. In that event, robin was injured and his breast was in holy blood. Holy blood means or shows the hero's torment in the fight to combat for religious purposes. Killing or hurting a robin means bad luck or breaking an egg is believed to something valuable of yours would also be broken beyond repair. Alas, robins are sometimes may be connected to something bad, for instance, their tapping at the window of sick and old person or entering and singing at a church may be a prediction of death. [26, p.189-192].

Object superstitions: Umbrella related superstitions are extant enough among cultures, for instance, some people avoid opening umbrella before going out; the origin of this wonderful tool backs to ancient Egypt where was and is always boiling weather, and straightly first umbrella-related superstitions were born there. Because Egyptians were religious people who believed in several Gods were afraid of opening umbrellas indoors regarded disrespectful to the God Of Sun, Ra, who would seek vengeance on the household in which the umbrella was opened. Getting married under umbrella means lifelong happiness and protection from evil spirits for a new couple in Western Cultures. However, the origin of umbrellas goes back to ancient Egypt where they were the thing of nobles. At that time they believed if the God of Sun straightly see the use of umbrellas by low class or not noble ones may not like and would see this act as sacrilegious [4, p.35-46]. This superstition has another explanation and it is rooted in 18th century when they were not automatic like current ones and were built with hard metal spokes and spring triggers and bigger than 21st century umbrellas, so they were dangerous enough to open indoors i.e. it was for safety reasons.

One of the oldest superstitions of nations is related with `mirror`. It is about avoiding to use broken mirror and this is more than 2700 years old superstition; Intriguingly, even if some people don't see themselves a particularly superstitious person, they, at least, probably say "bless you" when someone sneezes; It is of course because they consciously or unconsciously use this expression for avoiding evil hurts. Historically, people made up this expression since they thought while sneezing their soul might be stolen by devil. .

Water related superstitions exists among Turkish people, they splash a glass of water after the people who have left to travel. According to the words of Gomez, Cubans open a bottle of rum in New Year's Eve, they deliberately drop a few drops on the floor firstly before drinking to get the blessing of "the gone one". In Spain, they eat 12 grapes, no more, no less believing that will bring good luck and happiness.

Taking the sample of gifting superstitions, presenting yellow flowers in Russian and in some European countries is a sign of divorce, so some people never give yellow flowers to their loved ones. Due to the meaning and sound of some words, Chinese people avoid giving a clock or an umbrella as a gift. The sound of the word "clock" (zhong) is pronounced like 'end,' it is considered as the person who gives clock to someone may be wishing an end or death (song zhong)," Bernards explains. Similarly, this happens with an "umbrella" (san), which is pronounced as "separation or parting" (san), therefore so presenter is believed suggesting that gift taker a farewell"

Childbirth related superstitions: In English speaking countries childbirth, pregnancy has always been together with various rituals and superstitions. In our modern world most of those superstitions are still respected and used in order to sooth some superstitious people's spirit.

Sometimes, one can see proof in these superstitions use and benefits of them are frequently admitted by medical practitioners [2, p.622-627]. Everything begins with choosing pram for newly born, buying or choosing it before childbirth is safe and is believed to bring luck to the child. However, there is a but, the chosen pram should not be brought to home, before child comes home; it is believed to be unlucky to bring it before child comes home. There is another superstition in parts of North Yorkshire, for wishing bright and prosperous future to baby, relatives and family friends present a silver coin. Some superstitions are interestingly related to medicine and well being of new-born, grandparents advice to carry a new baby three times around the house to protect the child from colic. One more very delicate process in the early years of children is undoubtedly teething period when rubbing the gums with mum`s gold wedding-ring is believed to sooth the process. In one of the English speaking country, Australia equally respect cultural beliefs, superstitions and medical purposes in the time of childbirth. Mostly debate goes about sex of the child, regarding to one folk wisdom that if the abdomen of the would-be mum is lower, it is expected to have a baby girl; if it is higher, it is believed to expect baby boy [15, p. 279-291]; Yet there are other opposite, but provable arguments, for instance: most times the size or stance of the abdomen are believed to foretell the sex of the unborn child beforehand. This has been certainly belief of older generation; however, nowadays well-educated and modern parents do not consider them as plausible signs, as they see them as medical change in mother`s body.

Death or funeral superstitions: these sorts of superstitions include several odd rituals that come from fear of death and corpses. One of them is called “remove a corpse with feet first”, this dates back to Victorian England. The English believed that they should remove a body feet-first from a home for wishing bright way to the spirit of dead [22, p.285-295]. That ritual arose the fear that the departed would `look back` to follow another home member to death, so they just place coins on the eyelids of the dead. Another death related superstition is that people are often warned about covering up their mouths while yawning, when they pass a cemetery supposedly for preventing their body from entering the spirits of the dead. Birds are considered as harbingers of death according to other famous superstitions. They are believed to move between the sky and the earth, as if between temporal and spiritual world. For example, a bird flying into home through a window or door is considered to be a bad omen of death for someone within. Likewise, a bird sitting on a branch of a tree at home or tapping its against the glass may be an ominous sign. Some English people even believe that seeing an owl during the or hearing its hoot in daytime are considered to be another sign of fatality or death. Three on a match is so called another superstition, interestingly one of the Hollywood movie was based on this superstition in 1932. The movie states that if three people lights up from the same match, they are going to die undoubtedly. It is said that the origin of the belief dates back to Crimean War in 1850s: one soldier stroke a match alerted his enemy to his presence in the dark, the second soldier lighted his cigarette and gave the enemy to aim; and the third soldier received the fatal bullet.

Conclusion

As we studied above, the tendency of people towards superstitions is because of their sense of fear, feeling of unsafe or they mostly want their surroundings to make more predictable and another main reason of beliefs in superstitions is appeasing themselves. Studying the result of different examples, we may infer that cultural varieties may change the main concept of some superstitions and their purpose as well. Time has a huge impact on the use and beliefs in superstitions, such as in ancient times people were so more vulnerable to environmental forces that they seemed to have no choice to be superstitious. By being superstitious they somehow felt calm and safe. However, the chain of superstitions has not been proceeding over the centuries in the same way, as people become more knowledgeable and more aware of their surroundings. This period was forced by enlightenment. Various disputable questions were being raised by some scientists and they began researching in this field. Regarding with examples, we have analyzed number superstitions, which vary hugely among cultures. Taking example of some of them, we have comprehended that one number may be unlucky and be cursed in one culture, yet it is holy and appreciated in another.

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СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

5 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

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